

Spatial Audio in 360-degree videos: A Quality of Experience and Visual Attention Evaluation

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1. Introduction

Spatial audio is expected to revolutionize the realm of immersive media by completely transforming the way we perceive 360° videos. By skilfully blending audio cues with panoramic visuals, this intriguing combination is set to create a captivating environment that will significantly enhance immersion, engagement, and emotional resonance for viewers.

2. Visual Attention

Visual attention refers to the process by which our brain selects and focuses on specific visual stimuli within our field of view. In the context of 360° videos, spatial audio can (*or not?*) guide visual attention by attracting the viewer's gaze towards important or relevant elements within the video.

3. Quality of Experience

Quality of Experience (QoE) is a critical factor in determining user satisfaction in immersive media. QoE encompasses various aspects, such as visual quality, audio quality, interaction quality, and overall performance. Studies have shown that a positive QoE can significantly enhance user satisfaction, engagement, and immersion in immersive media. On the other hand, a negative QoE can lead to frustration, discomfort, and disengagement.

4. Relationship between Spatial Audio, Visual Attention and QoE

By strategically placing audio cues, creators can guide viewers' gaze towards important elements, improving their focus and engagement. This synchronization between audio and visual cues can enhance the overall quality of the viewing experience, making it more immersive and impactful.

5. Research Methodology

To investigate the impact of spatial audio on visual attention and quality of experience in 360° videos, participants were shown a series of such videos with non-spatial and varying levels of spatial audio cues. Head and eye-tracking technology was used to measure visual attention, and subjective ratings were collected to assess the quality of experience. By analyzing the data, valuable insights were gained on the relationship between spatial audio, visual attention, and overall viewer satisfaction.

6. Results and Analysis

The results* of the study showed a significant impact of spatial audio on visual attention and quality of experience in 360° videos. Subjective ratings indicated that participants perceived the videos with spatial audio as more realistic and enjoyable compared to those without spatial audio cues, leading to a more immersive and engaging experience.

**For details, please refer https://github.com/hirwaam/QoE_Visual-Attention_Spatial-Audio_360-videos*

7. Future Directions

Future work will involve conducting joint correlation analysis to explore the relationships between participants' head pose, pupil diameter, eye gaze, and heart rate data. This integrated approach can reveal intricate patterns and hidden connections that may not be apparent when analysing each factor individually.

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THANK YOU.

Santiago

Humberto

Maurice

Yves

STATION II